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Detection of Indicators That Correspond To Unmet Needs, Related To Employee Motivation

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Abstract

The rotation of personnel or rapid entry and exit of personnel is a phenomenon that is increasing, a problem for organizations, since it involves training and administration costs. In addition, time is required for the adaptation of the new staff to the dynamics of work. This research article seeks to detect the indicators that correspond to the unmet needs of workers that affect staff turnover in the grocery store "La Esmeralda". The analysis is based on the results of surveys applied to former workers of the organization. With regard to surveys, a quantitative descriptive study was conducted. The results obtained show that the causes that most affect the entry and rapid departure of personnel in the organization are: Monetary remuneration, personal satisfaction, learning, and development, which become the points to be taken into consideration by the company to make decisions that help reduce turnover for these causes mentioned.

Keywords: Staff Turnover, Motivation, Indicators, Job Satisfaction, Salary, Organization.

Introduction

The rapid entry and exit of personnel is a phenomenon that is increasing, a problem for companies, since it involves costs that are lost for the organization, these include training and administration. Likewise, time is required for the adaptation of the new personnel to the dynamics of work and their work culture, resulting in a lack of productivity and efficiency of the work team; therefore, it is important to identify what the threats and shortcomings are and implement measures in time to minimize their impact within the company.

Groceries "la esmeralda" was founded on August 18, 2018, its owners Mr. Romeo García López together with his wife Catalina Rivero Pérez opened the doors of this place to an entire community that did not have the necessary services of grocery stores, fue a good start for this place, since it was the main source of supplies of basic products for the home and had 10 employees, which, with the passage of time, constantly renounced, in a very short period of time.

This work is directed with the purpose of investigating and detecting if the main causes of the "Personnel Rotation" in this organization, (Groceries "La Esmeralda".), in which, in the opinion of the creator of this company, currently the percentage of rotation is fifty percent per year in the last four years, has to do with economic needs, communicative, satisfaction and personal development.

Chiavenato (2009) insists on saying that the rapid entry and exit of personnel, translates as the number of people who leave the organization voluntarily and involuntarily, for intrinsic or extrinsic causes in an established period of time which can be determined scientifically and impartially.

In addition to what Hernández, Cruz, Meza, and Cruz (2017) mention, the causes that frequently occur in staff turnover are classified into causes that are by their own decision or by force majeure, which are those that occur due to the resignation of the worker, death, disability, retirement, illness, personal reasons, dismissal, etc. This gives us to understand that the rotation of workers in most cases occurs because the work environment is negative and does not allow the development and growth of employees. It should also be borne in mind that some terms of activities are not because of the company, but represent decisions of the person himself, which is a consequence of his environment and needs.

There is a position according to Coronado (2006) cited in (Chaparro, Guzmán, Naizaque, Ortiz, & Jiménez, 2015, p. 20) that mentions that: The entry and exit of personnel can be favorable because this allows companies and organizations to have new personnel who provide different knowledge and perspectives. However, it can be expensive, which is why most organizations are interested in keeping it at a low rate.

According to what was written by Dominguez, López, and Hernández (2015), the most important factors observed in the rapid entry and exit of personnel are the economic spillover, professional development in the company and the relationship of personal life with work.

Koontz & Weilhrich (2007) in their work on motivation and human factors, refer to the fact that the motives of people are a conception of unconscious and conscious needs. Many of those are seen as first-hand needs, such as shelter and physiological needs. There are also other needs that are considered as second needs and these include companionship, self-realization, affection and self-esteem. From that point of view, the levels of satisfying these needs become different over time and together with people. Referring to the proposal that these scientists give us about motivation, we can understand that the instinct of the human being to satisfy their needs is constant throughout their lives, some can change, they can be in the first of their needs or until the last, or, to some people their needs never change.

With respect to the above, it can be perceived how these needs are also embodied in the theory of hierarchies of the needs of Maslow (1943), his work focuses and talks about how human needs have a hierarchy within themselves, which go up from the lowest levels to those at the top, And every time one of the needs of low levels is satisfied, it ceases to be a goal and the needs at the

higher level begin to dominate human behavior, this means that it begins to motivate until the moment of its self-realization.

Methods

In order to achieve the objective mentioned initially, to analyze the causes that affect the rapid entry and exit of personnel in the company Abarrotes "La Esmeralda", a quantitative methodological research design of a descriptivo type was used, resorting to the survey as a technique, which were applied to personnel who resigned between 2018 and 2022.

The survey is composed of five categories that derive from Abraham Maslow's so-called theory of human needs, which include: communication, learning and development, personal satisfaction, remuneration, work activities. From which the possible causes that are generating the rapid entry and exit of personnel were obtained using the analysis of the information obtained.

Each of the questions you have in the survey are composed of multiple-choice answers, with four options: agree, disagree, disagree a little, and disagree. For the analysis of the research, the results that had the least impact on the answers "agree" and "disagree" will be taken into account, because these answers are those that project a greater impact on staff turnover, that is, they are those statements where the percentage of acceptance by employees is lower in the different categories and they are less satisfied.

The survey was applied personally to the total population that had resigned from the company historically, which are a total of 20 people, which were easy to locate since, their addresses are in the vicinity of the company Abarrotes "la esmeralda", this information was provided directly by the owner of the company.

Development.

To carry out the training of the survey, a questionnaire was made based on Abraham Maslow's theory, called "human needs theory", which starts from the principle that human behavior resides in the person himself: his motivation to behave and act is derived from forces that exist in his mind.

According to Maslow, the needs of humans are distributed in a pyramid, which depends on the importance and dominance it has in human behavior. At the bottom of the pyramid are the most elementary and recurring needs, known as primary, while at the top are the most sophisticated and abstract secondary needs.

Maslow (1943) shows the level of hierarchies: psychological needs, security needs, possessiveness and love needs, esteem needs, and self-actualization needs." (P.85-96). The needs that start as a basis are the psychological, in these are the sustenance of human life, so they are taken as primordial and the person will seek to satisfy them first before the others, turning that need as the primordial and important leaving the others behind.

This theory of Maslow (1943) is an approach to the needs that individuals in an entity seek to satisfy with urgent priority, that is, depending on the level of need, a greater probability of having rotation will be observed, thus, it will be presented that to what extent the organization will generate the necessary tools so that the employee meets his need and can continue climbing in the hierarchy of needs.

The descriptive research method has been used in other studies, Krackhardt, McKenna, Porter, & Steers (1981) used the survey as a tool to identify the rapid entry and exit of personnel induced by supervisors of the firm. Chiang & Ojeda (2013) through the survey obtained information that illustrated the relationship between satisfaction and productivity. Cabrera et. Al (2011) used the survey to find the relationship between

staff turnover and productivity and effectiveness. Carrillo, Solano, Martínez & Gómez (2013) ran a survey of 546 professionals in order to find the degree of satisfaction of the work they do, Sil Choi & Mi Kim (2014) in his work conducted surveys with similar questions in categories such as: job satisfaction, intention to retire, work commitment with the organization.

Result

With respect to the result of the survey applied was obtained as main categories to be observed as main factors in the rapid entry and exit of personnel in recent years in Abarrotes "La Esmeralda" are the following: remuneration, with an acceptance by former workers of 25%, Personal satisfaction with 30% and Learning and Development with 35%; These categories mentioned above were the ones that presented the lowest percentage in The qualification "agree" and "disagree", i.e. they are the least satisfied workers are therefore those who are influencing staff turnover.

Graph 1. Percentage of the five categories assessed in the questions.

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Own elaboration

Knowing the categories that obtained the lowest rating within the organization: Remuneration, Personal Satisfaction and Learning and development, it can be argued that these are the causes that have the greatest impact on the rapid entry and exit of personnel of Abarrotes "La Esmeralda" coinciding with written at the beginning of this article where remuneration and personal satisfaction are those that generate a great impact on decision-making to leave their position work.

If we analyze the results obtained, with the level of hierarchies of needs of Maslow (1943), we can observe that the salary is part of the psychological needs, meanwhile, personal satisfaction and Learning and development is part of the needs of esteem and the relationship life and work is found in the needs of possessiveness and love. This is related to the percentage of approval by workers, since the main need of people is to cover basic needs, which are satisfied with the monetary remuneration of their work.

Conclusion

The satisfaction of the needs of workers is a key to the success of a company, since they are the most significant resource within it, the degree of customer satisfaction depends on them, they must be in constant stimulation so that consequently this has a positive mark in their daily work.

The research method carried out helped to be consummated with the general objective of this work, being able to find the indicators that correspond to the unsatisfied needs of the former workers of Abarrotera "Esmeralda", since the increased e the turnover in the personnel that has been having in the few years of work of the organization is considerable. These indicators found were: Monetary remuneration, personal satisfaction and Learning and development.

With the information that was found and which was analyzed, it is possible to consider that the origins of the rapid entry and exit of personnel can be reduced with strategies aimed mainly at more competitive salaries, execute training that helps professional growth, make workers see the success of the company as their own, time elasticity, establish new hierarchical levels, among others, thus becoming a recognized and competitive company in the professional market, as long as they are applied.

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